

Managing the Residual Load Imbalance and Clock Frequency to Save Energy on Iterative Applications

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Abstract. Power Demand and Energy Consumption of large-scale systems are current concerns in the High Performance Computing area. Aiming to increase the efficiency of these systems and better managing the load and energy consumption, load balancing strategies have been proposed as a good solution. In response to this challenge, we developed an energy-aware load balancer called ENERGYLB to manage and reduce the power demand and save energy of systems when iterative applications with imbalanced load are executed. Our proposed load balancer combines dynamic load balancing with DVFS techniques in order to reduce the clock frequency of underloaded computing cores which experience some residual imbalance even after tasks are remapped. Tests carried out with two applications show that ENERGYLB results in low overhead, power reductions of 7% in average and energy saving of 6% in average when used together with other CHARM++ load balancers.

Keywords: Load Balancing, DVFS, Power Demand, Energy Consumption, Energy Saving

1 Introduction

The simulation of large scientific applications is increasing in HPC systems and cloud platforms. In this context, to increase the accuracy of the results, more data and variables are used, demanding more and more processing power. To attend this demand, HPC community is building Exascale systems by scaling the current technology, which requires high power to work. In this way, a global effort has risen to try to build energy efficient systems.

In this scenario, load balancing strategies emerge as an important means to achieve efficient utilization of resources through better management of load, which makes it possible to reduce the total execution time of applications the

consequently save energy, once energy is saved when systems resources are used for a shorter time. However, we can observe the presence of a small imbalance after applying some balancing strategies. So, it is possible to achieve even greater energy savings through exploration these residual imbalances and fine tune the voltage and frequency of cores accordingly. In this case, our approaches aims to reduce the instantaneous power demand of the systems while maintaining a similar performance.

Several scientific applications can be designed taking into account the load distributions and allow an regular computational load. However, a large majority of these applications have tasks with different processing demands, which makes the load distribution among the processors more difficult. In this context, different strategies have been developed to mitigate these imbalanced workloads and achieve an efficient use of all available parallel resources. On the other hand, most of these load balancing approaches aim to reduce execution time using only computational load, neglecting power demand and total energy consumption.

In the state of the art, different approaches have been developed to reduce the power demand of parallel system while different load balancer approaches have been used to reduce the total energy consumption reducing the application execution time by improving the load distribution among cores. However, these approaches are used separately. Several works have used DVFS to save energy, however this technique can result in performance degradation and an increase of the application runtime. Other proposals have applied load balancing strategies to mitigate the imbalanced workloads and achieve an efficient use of all parallel resources, which reduce the overall execution time, and, consequently, save energy. Our energy efficient approach make the case that both strategies, load balancing and DVFS, could be used together over iterative applications to save energy. It identifies the residual imbalance after task migrations and then reduce the cores clock during the execution to achieve better gains over other load balancer algorithms. In this way, energy improvements are achieved due the reduction of average power demand during the execution.

In this paper, we present and validate over two applications our energy-aware load balancer called ENERGYLB, which minimize the total energy consumption when applied over iterative applications with imbalanced loads. The results show that our energy-aware load balancer, by combining load balancing with DVFS, is able to reduce the average power demand during the execution, saving energy when it is applied together with other state-of-the-art algorithms.

The remaining sections of this paper are organized as follows. Section 2 discusses some of the related works on DVFS and load balancing strategies. The proposal of the our energy-aware load balancer (ENERGYLB) and its implementation details are presented in Section 3. In Section 4 we discuss the evaluation methodology, the real applications and state of the art load balancers used in the experiments. In Section 5 we address the results obtained from the experiments. Finally, Section 6 emphasizes the scientific contribution of the work and notes several challenges that we can address in the future.

2 Related Work

Many researches have been developed aiming to reduce the demand of power of entire large systems aiming to improve efficiency while these run iterative applications. In response to this challenge, load balancing and Dynamic voltage and frequency scaling (DVFS) have been applied together as an alternative to save energy.

Processor consumes significant amount of power compared. In order to reduce power consumption, different studies have been proposed the DVFS approach. Silva *et al.* [21] proposed a methodology to find energy-optimal frequency and number of active cores to run single-node HPC applications. Gupta *et al.* [7] proposed a framework leverages the workload profile information together with power constraints to compute the voltage–frequency settings according a power budget. Acun *et al.* [1] proposed an intelligent energy efficient runtime module which uses a fine-grained function level per-core DVFS approach. Their module aims to find the optimal frequency for each phase of the application over the first few iterations and applies the optimal frequency for each function. Test on Haswell processors show gains from 4% up to 35% on total energy over chip-level DVFS. Bhalachandra *et al.* [3] present an Adaptive Core-specific Runtime that dynamically adapts core frequencies to workload characteristics. Their approach uses existing core-specific power controls like software-controlled clock modulation and per-core Dynamic Voltage Frequency Scaling (DVFS). Experiments on benchmarks and a real world application show an overall 20% improvement in energy efficiency with less than 1% increase in execution time on 1024 cores using per-core DVFS. Kin *et al.* [15] proposed a realistic DVFS performance prediction method and a practical DVFS control policy (eDVFS) that aims to minimize total energy consumption in multi-core processors. Their experimental results show that eDVFS can save a substantial amount of energy compared with Linux on-demand. Imes *et al.* [11] find a meeting performance requirements with power capping is more challenging than using DVFS because the relationship between power and performance. Huang *et al.* [9] aim to minimise the energy consumption while keeping all deadlines satisfied. They have proposed a DVFS-nondependent scheduling algorithm which prioritises tasks of high energy consumption during reassignment with slack time, a DVFS-weakly dependent scheduling algorithm, which finds an appropriate frequency for each processor in an iterative manner. Their proposed scheduling approaches were evaluated with directed acyclic graph-based applications reducing the energy cost compared to their existing counterparts while all deadlines remain satisfied.

In the load balancing context, some approaches aim to improve the performance of parallel applications through task migrations. However, few researches have made some efforts to further improve the energy consumption together with load balancing [10,14,23,19]. Zhai *et al.* [22] present different load-balancing algorithms for compute-intensive and targeted for deployment on exascale platforms what aims to eliminate load imbalance in different processors and to speed up the makespan. Evaluations of the proposal strategy show that the time becomes faster by a factor of up to 9.97 and the performance was improved by a factor of

up to 1.42. Aupy [2] proposed energy-aware scheduling models to schedule tasks under reliability and makespan constraints. They designed and evaluated them using simulations with different heuristics based on the failure probability, the task weights, and the processor speeds. Enokido *et al.* [5] proposed to select a virtual machine for each request process according to computation type application. Their approach collects a state of some process on every virtual machine to estimate the energy spent of each server. The proposal algorithm was evaluated and shown to be reduced in the total energy of a server cluster compared with the energy consumption laxity based and basic round-robin algorithms. Goel *et al.* [6] proposed a model that uses CPU performance counters and CPU temperature to generate accurate per-core power estimates in real-time. They showed that the model can be used to guide scheduling decisions in power-aware resource managers. Hartog *et al.* [8] studied the relationship between CPU temperature and energy consumption in clusters and provided a method of estimating the power consumption of the system. This method was then used to implement a MapReduce framework that can evaluate the current status of each node and dynamically react to estimated power usage without having to rely on readings from expensive power monitoring hardware affixed to each node in the cluster.

Different to cited papers, our new variant approach uses DVFS after load balancing strategy to improve the performance and to reduce the energy consumption by exploiting residual imbalances of iterative and parallel applications, different from previous versions [16][18]. This new variant also aims to reduce the cost of task migrations. The performance and energy efficiency of our approach were also analyzed on two iterative applications running on top of a real platform.

3 Energy-Aware Load Balancer

Simulating scientific applications often produces tasks with different computational loads. Thus, when these tasks are executed, they can generate load imbalance. Aiming to mitigate this context, load balancing approaches have been used which making a better load distribution among the available processors in the system. Current load balancing strategies try to reduce load imbalance by moving tasks between cores or processors, which incurs overheads to data collection, decision making and mainly tasks migration. It all takes time and also affects the total execution time and consequently the total of energy spent to perform an application.

Aiming to reduce the execution time, energy consumption and take into account the current power demand to make their decision-making we proposed our *Energy-Aware Load Balancer*, called of the (ENERGYLB) [16]. This version implements *Fine-Grained EnergyLB* (FG-ENERGYLB) and *Coarse-Grained EnergyLB* (CG-ENERGYLB) approaches suitable for homogeneous systems using our *Energy_Daemon* and *libEnergy* as shown in Figure 1. Considering that the organization of current parallel systems are built using different architectures, we proposed a variant called of the HENERGYLB that is suitable for platforms

composed of heterogeneous processors which allow per-processor DVFS [18,17]. This variant considers a flat view of the underlying platform, balancing the load among all processors and performing DVFS on each individual processors. When the load imbalance is considerably high, it not migrate tasks, it rely on currently available load balancers to better distribute the tasks among the processors. On the other hand, when migrating tasks is not beneficial, we adjust the clock frequency of underloaded processors individually to save energy. Although this approach allows for a finer tune of the load and frequency.

In this paper, we propose a second variant of the ENERGYLB approach. It also takes into account that both strategies, load balancing and DVFS, are used together over iterative applications to save energy by reducing the average power demand during the execution. The new variant, different from the previous ones, identifies the residual imbalance after task migrations and then reduce the cores clock to a new execution achieving so better gains over previous load balancer versions.

Fig. 1. ENERGYLB Implementation [16]

3.1 EnergyLB Algorithm

For decision making, this new approach takes into account the same three input parameters used in previous versions [16][18]. The first one, (*lb*), is the load balancer that is being performed to reduce the load imbalance. The second one, (*max_freq*), is the maximum frequency that can be set to a processor. The third one, (*thrd*), is the *threshold* used to decide whether to perform DVFS.

So, in each call of the load balancer, first a *lb* is performed. After, our new variant identifies the residual imbalance and verified if it exceeds the *threshold* determining a new frequency to each processor to keep running.

To make decisions, at each load balancing step, the strategies get the *residual imbalanced load* and *current clock frequency* of each core. Having completed

this phase, ENERGYLB determines the minimum (*min_Wload*) and maximum (*max_Wload*) weighted loads of all cores.

Finally, it decides, if *residual imbalanced load* is greater *threshold*, to perform DVFS to adjust a new clock frequency to the core.

So, by updating the frequency of the processor according to their residual imbalance loads, ENERGYLB reduces the average power demand of the cores during the execution, consequently, saving energy.

3.2 Implementation Details

To implement this new variant of the ENERGYLB we have used the CHARM++ parallel runtime system [12]. This framework provides a simple API that can be used to implement load balancers without changing the source code of the applications. The instrumented data load can be dynamically obtained during the application execution through the use of the API.

Similar to the two old versions, our proposed variant also uses the two modules as shown in Figure 1. The first, called of *Energy Daemon* is responsible for gathering power and energy measurements through the Intel’s Running Average Power Limit (RAPL). And the second is a *Lib Energy* that offers an interface to get system information such as the maximum frequency that can be set to a core or processor, to set the clock frequency of individual processors/cores or to set a specific Linux governor [16,18].

4 Evaluation Methodology

4.1 Experimental Environment

The experiments were conducted on a platform designed by Dell. Our platform is composed of 7 NUMA nodes. Each node has two Intel Xeon E5-2640 v2 Ivy Bridge x86-64 processors with 8 physical cores. There are 10 clock frequency levels available in this processor, allowing us to vary the clock frequency of the processor from 1.2 GHz up to 2.0 GHz. Each node has 64 GB of DDR3 memory. Overall, this platform has 112 physical cores and 448 GB DDR3 memory.

The platform runs an Debian operating system with kernel 4.19.0.20 installed. All applications as well as the CHARM++ version 7.0.0 and programming model were compiled with GCC 8.3.0. The results presented in Section 5 are the average of at least 10 runs. The relative error was less than 5% using a 95% statistical confidence by Student’s t-distribution.

4.2 Applications

To evaluate our Energy-Aware Load Balancers, we selected two real-world applications and perform tests measuring the runtime, power demand and total energy consumption. This application were chosen due to their varied range of communication patterns and workload characteristics. The description of the applications is given below:

- *lb_test* provides a scenario to simulate a variety of science and engineering problems with an imbalanced load. It also can use different communication patterns among the processors. To perform the tests, we have used a random communication graph [13,4];
- *ComprehensiveBench* is a highly configurable synthetic benchmark that can be used to create iterative applications according to different parameters such as the number of tasks, iterations, communication graph, task loads and message sizes [20].

Input parameters Our selected applications start its execution in an imbalanced state. Table 1 summarizes the imbalance type and initial state of the applications selected for the load balancer evaluation.

Table 1. Benchmarks and real world applications characteristics.

Application	Imbalance Type	Initial State
<i>lb_test</i>	load	imbalanced
<i>ComprehensiveBench</i>	load/communication	imbalanced

Table 2 summarizes the characteristics of the applications and parameters used in our experiments. Different load balancing frequencies have been chosen for different applications in order to strike a balance between the benefits of remapping tasks and the overheads of moving tasks and computing a new task mapping.

Table 2. Summary of the input parameters of benchmarks and real applications.

Application	Tasks	Iterations	LB Frequency (Iterations)
<i>lb_test</i>	1000	250	10
<i>ComprehensiveBench</i>	50	50	5

4.3 Load Balancers

We applied our energy-aware load balancer along with different standard load balancers available in CHARM++. The rationale behind that is to evaluate the energy savings that can be obtained by exploiting residual imbalances of these load balancers. To compare the power demand and energy consumption results,

we selected the load balancers GREEDYLB that have a greedy algorithm, REFINELB that use a limit of task migrations, METISLB that make a partition of the object communication graph. ROTATELB that move objects to the next available PE.

5 Experimental Results

This section presents the performance evaluation and the energy efficiency achieved by our energy-aware load balancer on the experimental platform presented in the last section.

Different values for the threshold (*thrld*) were tested with all the selected applications but, due to space constraints, we do not show in this paper a sensitivity analysis for this parameter. Although the overall results did not vary too much within a reasonable range, we chose *thrld*=1.8 because it behaved, on average, the best on the majority of the workloads. In the following sections we evaluate the performance and energy efficiency of ENERGYLB on selected applications.

5.1 EnergyLB Evaluation

In this section, we evaluate the benefits of ENERGYLB on applications presented in the previous section. So, in this section, we provide an analysis of total runtime and power demand over total energy consumption when ENERGYLB is used over applications in the system aiming to reduce the effects of load imbalance and reduce the average power demand to save energy.

We have evaluated the total executing time, power demand, and the total energy consumption of application when executed in the 3 scenarios: (i) without any load balancer (noLB); (ii) using the standard load balancers available in CHARM++ (GREEDYLB, REFINELB, METISLB and SCOTCHLB); and (iii) applying the ENERGYLB to adjust the frequency according to their loads and their residual load imbalance (LB + ENERGYLB).

– Runtime Evaluation

Figure 2 shows the total execution time achieved with the adoption of the ENERGYLB load balancer. We realise an average time-overhead increment of 0.53% when ENERGYLB was used together with the 4 load balancers selected for tests with *lb.test*.

GREEDYLB was responsible for reducing the time from 185.06 seconds to 136.12 seconds, which represented a 26.45% gain. Running the proposal load balancer ENERGYLB in conjunction with GREEDYLB the overhead (0.803 s) increased the total execution time by 136.92 seconds. Even so, the gains stood at 26.01%. Similar gains were achieved for REFINELB and METISLB.

A similar behavior occurs when using the proposed load balancer with the *ComprehensiveBench* application. ENERGYLB presented an average overhead of

Fig. 2. Runtime execution for each application with ENERGYLB.

0.37% when used together with the four load balancers selected for the tests with the *ComprehensiveBench*. Likewise, this overhead value is offset by gains achieved with load balancers available in CHARM++ which reduced the time on average by 17.76%.

– Power Evaluation

On the other hand, the use of our proposal ENERGYLB, was able to analyze the residual load imbalance, after the application of CHARM++ load balancers, and then to reduce the clock frequencies and consequently, reduce the demand power in average 6.68% when running *lb_test* application.

Fig. 3. Average Power Demand for each application with ENERGYLB.

When our proposal ENERGYLB is applied in the execution of the *ComprehensiveBench* application, a greater load imbalance was noticed after the migration of tasks between the cores used. Thus, the adoption of ENERGYLB was more

effective, reducing the average power demand by 7.16%.

– Energy Evaluation

Fig. 4. Total Energy Consumption for each application with ENERGYLB.

Our main goal is energy saving. In this way, when applied the ENERGYLB along the load balancers available on CHARM++, the total energy consumption of *lb_test* and *ComprehensiveBench* were reduced by 6.18% and 6.82% respectively, as depicted in Figures 4(a) and 4(b).

This energy consumption reduction is achieved once than ENERGYLB was employed over selected applications and it has a low overhead, around of 0.4% as depicted in Figure 2, and a power reduction in average of 7% as depicted in Figure 3.

6 Conclusions

There is an increasing use of large-scale systems in simulations and resolution of real problems aiming to achieve runtime reduction and increased the accuracy. However, the use of these systems demand high power which result in significant energy costs. In this context, power demand is currently a critical concern in the build of new HPC systems.

In this paper, aims attend to power concern, we focused on manager computational load, reducing power demand of systems when parallel and iterative applications are performed. We have proposed a new energy-aware load balancers called ENERGYLB which reduce the power demand of cores during the execution, saving energy of parallel systems. Our strategy take into account the residual imbalances after load migrations on iterative applications and adjust the clock frequency of underloaded cores through DVFS.

Experimental results using two scientific applications present energy consumption reduction when our ENERGYLB load balancer was applied to four load balancers. ENERGYLB is able to reduce the power demand in average of 7% on two applications saving energy in up to 6.8% when used together with the selected CHARM++ load balancers.

In new researches, this work can be extended in different directions. One approach would be in the building of a load balancer strategy that performs both load migrations and clock frequency adjust in each load balancing step according to cost of task migrations and cost of to apply DFVS. On the same line, another approach would be investigate and take into account to make load decisions the cost to to performs task migrations between cores of the same processor or migrate tasks between all processors of a cloud system. Finally, we also intend to evaluate the benefits of ENERGYLB on other real-world applications and large-scale system.

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